

Ollaberry,
Crimms Hill,
Great Missenden,
Bucks,
ENGLAND.
9/2/72.

Dear Mr. Sarfaraz,

I hope that you and your family are well, and that your excavations are proving successful.

Last year, you remember, I told you that I thought there was a reference in one of the ancient geographers to the Achaemenid Palace at Kazerun. I could not find the referencr then, but now in England I have found it and in case you do not already know it I give it here:

Arrian Indica Chapter 39 describing the voyage of Alexander's fleet up the Persian Gulf:

" From Mesembria(Bushehr) they sailed and after a voyage of about 200 stades anchored at Taoce on the river Granis. Inland from there was a Persian Royal Palace about 200 stades from the mouth of the river."

There is no doubt from the position given that this refers to the palace you are excavating at Kazerun.

When I was in Teheran Mr. Yakhmai very kindly showed me some drawings of the pottery from the Palace. One glazed sherd which is also very common at Bushehr is of a type found at Siraf in the late Sassanian Period, and might show that the palace was still used at that period..

I hope that I shall be able to see you at the Iranology Congress in Oxford in September.

With best wishes.

Yours sincerely

Andrew Williamson